

BIOFIN-EU-project.eu

BIOFIN-EU

PROTECTING AND RESTORING BIODIVERSITY USING MAINSTREAM FINANCE

D1.1: Project Management Plan Handbook

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Funded by
the European Union

Grant Agreement No.	101135476
Project Acronym	BIOFIN-EU
Project Title	Protecting and Restoring Biodiversity using Mainstream Finance
Type of action	HORIZON-RIA
Horizon Europe Call Topic	HORIZON-CL6-2023-BIODIV-01-9
Start – ending date	1 January 2024 - 31 December 2026
Project Website	BIOFIN-EU-project.eu
Work Package	University of Limerick
WP Lead Beneficiary	John Garvey
Relevant Task(s)	D1.1 Project Management Handbook
Deliverable type Dissemination level	R – Report
Due Date of Deliverable	30 April 2024
Actual Submission Date	30 April 2024
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Document History

Date	Version	Changes	Contributor(s)
DD/MM/YYYY	V0.1	[Description of changes]	Contributors' Name and Surname (Partner)
DD/MM/YYYY	V0.X	[Description of changes]	Contributors' Name and Surname (Partner)

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Title: BIOFIN-EU – Unlock Finance to Protect and Restore Biodiversity

Type of action: HORIZON Research and Innovation Action

Topic: HORIZON-CL6-2023-BIODIV-01-9: Biodiversity, economics and finance: unlocking financial flows towards reversing of biodiversity loss

Start date of project: January 1st, 2024; Duration: 36 months

Executive Summary

BIOFIN-EU focuses on redirecting financial resources for biodiversity recovery and protection by creating a unified framework that categorises nature-based solutions, streamlines the investment process, and incorporates a data analytics and underwriting engine. Real-life case studies validate the approach, contributing to a dual green and digital transition that simplifies transactions. Outcomes will identify taxonomy gaps and provide evidence-based policy recommendations for the European financial services industry, supporting the EU's biodiversity goals. The timing of the project is from January 1st, 2024, for a duration of 3 years, specific milestones and KPIs are provided in the project schedule. The project is EU funded and will involve partnering with a variety of representatives globally with the required acumen to drive the project with purpose and efficiency, as listed in page 3. This deliverable defines all the necessary mechanisms and structures for the management and administrative coordination of the project with emphasis on the governance, change management, communication plan, project calendar, stages, milestones and reporting roles and responsibilities for all the partners is also made. The project management plan outlines the approach and framework for successfully executing the project. By adhering to the plan and continuously monitoring its progress, we aim to achieve the project goals within the specified timeline and budget.

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Glossary of terms and abbreviations used.

CR	Change Requests
DNSH	Do No Significant Harm
EI	Expected Impact
EO	Expected Outcomes
ER	Expected Results
EU	European Union
FSC	Forest Stewardship Council
IoT	Internet of Things
IPBES	Intergovernmental science-policy Platform on Biodiversity and Ecosystem Services
IPCC	Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change
KER	Key Exploitable Results
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
KR	Key Results
LS	Learning Sites
MCDA	multi-criteria decision making
NBS	Nature Based Solutions
NFRD	Non-Financial Reporting Directive
NP	National Park
NWFP	Non-Wood Forest Products
PAI	Principal Adverse Impact
PC	Project Coordinator
PM	Project Manager
PO	Project Officer
PPP	Public-Private Partnerships

RIA	Registered Investment Advisor
SFDR	Sustainable Finance Disclosure Regulation
SFT	Sustainable Finance Taxonomy
SN	Specific Needs
SOE	State-Owned Enterprises
TRL	Technology Readiness Level
UNIPD	Strategic Objectives
VBC	Voluntary Biodiversity Credits
VFM	Voluntary Biodiversity Credits
WP	Work Package

1. Introduction

1.1. Document Scope

The purpose of this document is to provide a single point of reference on the management and quality that will be governed during the course of the project. It defines the project organization, roles and responsibilities with emphasis on the quality control and quality assurance activities that will be carried out. It describes how the project will execute its day-to-day activities from a quality perspective and ensures that standards, processes and procedures are defined, and their execution is continuously monitored and improved. A reference to all the necessary mechanisms and structures for the management and administrative coordination of the project capitalizing on the governance, change management, communication plan, project calendar, stages, milestones, and reporting roles and responsibilities for all the partners is also made. In case of inconsistencies between this document and the Grant Agreement or Consortium Agreement, the most recent version of the Grant Agreement or Consortium Agreement take precedence over this handbook.

1.2. Project Summary

Problem Statement: Nature is essential for human existence and our quality of life and society is directly and indirectly dependent on the natural environment, its biodiversity and ecosystem services. We now know that the design of the globalised financial system, which seeks to optimise financial return irrespective of its secondary impacts, is contributing to large-scale biodiversity loss and bringing our biosphere closer to collapse. Yet our modern economics lives are directed by financial institutions and markets. They influence the products we consume (via corporate financing choices), where and how we live (via lending and insurance products), access to energy, food and transport services (via corporate and public enterprise investment) and where we place our savings (via asset management). Behind this front door, the financial system is formed from networks of financial institutions and intermediaries deploying decision-making tools and instruments that direct and redirect the flow of capital. The EU Green Deal and the Sustainable Finance Taxonomy (SFT) provide an important starting point for placing a bound on the destructive power of capital and redirecting financial flows towards nature-positive economic activity.

BIOFIN-EU will use a multi-actor approach to create impact through a science-led dashboard for nature-positive financial decision support. Built with and for six key groups: ecologists, data scientists, financial and accounting experts, citizens, providers of nature-based solutions (NBS) as well as investors (financial institutions, non-financial companies (NFCs), State-Owned Enterprises (SOEs), the Dashboard will help actors navigate large-scale financing challenges and to develop, replicate, scale out and strengthen NBS-investment,

creating a more sustainable, vibrant, resilient and healthy planet and supporting the EU’s biodiversity restoration ambitions.

1.3. Project Scope and Outcomes

BIOFIN-EU develops and tests novel approaches in biodiversity and ecosystem services (ES) data capture, aggregation and analytics to help reduce transaction and reporting costs associated with biodiversity-linked finance. It aims to thoroughly test methods and tools that may significantly help address the grand scientific, economic and societal challenges associated with the restoration and protection of biodiversity. It will achieve this, through a number of key objectives: i) To develop and test solutions able to record and share meaningful, reliable and useful biodiversity and ES data from heterogeneous and dispersed/scarce data sources with minimal delay and in the appropriate format, ii) To understand the preferences and regulatory requirements of capital owners, financial institutions and NBS-providers so that relevant governance aspects are designed into business models and financial instruments and associated enabling technologies and tools, iii) To develop of trustworthy, accurate, and fair data sharing of biodiversity and ES outcomes to reduce transaction costs and other barriers to nature finance, iv) To design and test new business models and biodiversity-linked investments that maintain protections for NBS-providers and their communities while securing long-horizon benefits for NBS-promoters, v) integrate relevant processes, systems and reporting and disclosure requirements to help BIOFIN-EU support organisations in directing financial flows towards biodiversity protection and restoration, vi) To build knowledge and skills among current and future finance professionals and decision-makers and build a community to advance the implementation of the regulations to codevelop solutions and accelerate the financial flow of funds towards for biodiversity-linked activity, vii) opportunities arising from specifically, nature positive investment will be examined by analysis preferences among shareholders, bond investors and consumers (corporate finance/private equity) as well as retirees (fund management) and transition costs associated with the re-allocation of finance from destructive economic activity will be examined in greater detail. Financial models associated with corporate performance as well as fund management performance will be examined here.

Figure 1. BIOFIN-EU Project Overview

Through the *NBS Dashboard*, BIOFIN-EU will establish the EU as the global frontrunner in deploying private finance to protect and restore biodiversity. The *Dashboard* provides a unifying technology and

framework to identify drivers and implementation gaps for the SFT, challenge existing theories and practices which currently constrain investment in Nature-Based Solutions (NBS) and activate novel business models and approaches that can redirect the flow of finance towards the protection and restoration of biodiversity. *The Dashboard* will comprise three modules, including; i) an interactive *NBS Database* to categorise NBS and provide stakeholders in nature-positive investments with a systematic tool to record, monitor and report outcomes; ii) *Business Builder* within which sits a ‘Menu of Good Governance’ options and a ‘Library of Stakeholder Engagement’ will provide mechanisms for establishing, expanding and maintaining corporate participation in Nature Based Solutions, and iii) the ‘*Data Analytics & Underwriting Engine*’ that provides the tools and methodologies for calculating costs, benefits and impacts of NBS-investment.

Figure 2. The NBS Dashboard

1.3.1. Strategic Objectives

There are 7 Strategic Objectives of BIOFIN-EU, namely:

- SO#1: Generate increased understanding, knowledge and awareness of nature-positive investing and identify the enabling market conditions for (EO2) by collating existing knowledge and 8 BIOFIN-EU learning sites to categorise NBS and provide a tool (NBS Dashboard) for NBS investors to monitor outcomes (WP2, 3 & 4).
- SO#2 Identify and help understand the success factors, drivers, costs, accruing from the mobilisation of mainstream finance (EO1), introduce new knowledge methodologies and tools (EO2) to increase understanding and know-how of economic actors (EO3) by co-designing and activating the Business Model Builder (KER2, WP3,4&6) for financial institutions and service providers, NBS providers and funders, policy makers and researchers.
- SO#3 Better understand the opportunities and gaps in implementing the SFT (EO2), and help integrate existing and new certification procedures as well as the data and accounting standards into decision-making processes by integrating such tools and metrics into the design of business models (WP5)
- SO#4 Expand the set of methodologies and tools that support the implementation of the EU strategy for financing the transition to a sustainable economy (EO2) by challenging existing approaches to modelling the risk and return tradeoff and integrating biodiversity and ES risk characteristics into the Data Analytics and Underwriting Engine (KER3).
- SO#5 Create, test and validate the enabling conditions for stakeholders to undertake privately financed nature-positive activities by collating all of the resources, tools and innovations developed in BIOFIN-EU (O1-4) into an accessible support platform, The NBS Dashboard (KER1-3), with tailored

access portals for each key stakeholder group: NBS providers, NFCs, financial institutions and services, policy makers and researchers (WP5, 6).

- SO#6 Identify and understand the features that are necessary for of nature-positive investments to qualify for large-scale investment and promotes a holistic approach that considers nature’s essential contributions to other objectives (e.g. water security, health, food) by developing multi-criteria decision making (MCDA) approaches for investors and incorporating aggregation mechanisms into the NBS Dashboard that support selection and portfolio optimisation that maximises investment impact across criteria and sectors.
- SO#7 Increase awareness and know-how and resolve knowledge and skills gaps in the implementation of the SFT and Technical Screening and DNSH principle (EO3) and contribute to the implementation of the EU biodiversity strategy for 2030 by designing skills and knowledge accelerators (KER4) for European financial institutions and markets that draw on real-life business simulations and related tools and instruments available in The NBS Dashboard (KER1-3) and through a series of stakeholder interactions (workshops, questionnaires, interviews) consolidate best practice and identify the policy levers that are needed to incentivise investment and unblock impediments to progress.

1.3.2. Milestones and Deliverables

The project's outcomes will align with the objectives through successful milestone and deliverable attainment. To follow are two tables on the specific Milestones and Deliverables as per the Description of the Action (DoA) in the Grant Agreement (GA).

Milestone No	Milestone Name	Lead Beneficiary	Means of Verification	Due Date (month)
1	Kick-off event	1-UL	Meeting agenda, minutes and press releases	2
2	Strong project brand established	5-RAINNO	Visual Identity, website, social media pages, Communication Strategy (Deliverable WP7 Dissemination, exploitation, communication plan)	6
3	Initial user requirements determined	3-UGOT	Requirements roadmap available on BIOFIN website	6
4	Learning-Site Use-Case Plan	2-NATURALIS	First release of supporting documentation on learning site NBS activity (Deliverable WP6 Framework of NBS categorization and best practice)	9
5	NBS Categorization and Best Practice	2-NATURALIS	Publication of framework of NBS categorization and best practice biodiversity data tools (Deliverable WP2 Framework of NBS categorization and best practice)	12
6	Identification of biodiversity and ecosystem valuation & NBS decision support barriers	3-UGOT	Report publication will be a key result that informs external stakeholders about the first stage of BIOFIN's activity and builds a community to monitor and participate in the activation phase of the research.	18

7	Biodiversity U/W framework: Final Release	4-UM	Machine learning models deployed as modules in the NBS Dashboard to support lending, insurancepricing, investment	20
8	Biodiversity Data: Systems Capability	1-UL	Publication of report on Financial Institutions & Markets systems capability (WP5 deliverable Report on 'Financial Institutions & Markets Biodiversity Data Systems Capability')	24
9	NBS Dashboard - Final Release	1-UL	Dashboard demonstrating NBS-decision supportfor NBS-providers and NBS-promoters (WP2 deliverable Framework of NBS categorization and best practice, WP3 Deliverable Biodiversity and ecosystem valuation classification and deliverable Report on NBS stakeholder'seconomic valuation) & WP5 deliverable NBS Dashboard Proof-of-Concept Design and Implementation (lean approach with highfrequency feedback loops with NBS users))	30
10	Civil Society Forum on Nature Finance – First Report	13-QUB	Launch of first report from Civil Society Forum on Nature Finance. (WP6 deliverable Policy Report on 'NBS Multifunctionality, Business Model Design and EU Policy')	34
11	Ethics Report	1-UL	Production of initial Ethics Report to ensure that the project follows the appropriate ethics procedures and will provide two reports during the course of the project (second report in M24).The Chair will provide help to implement ethics and provide guidance on informed consent, data access and ethics relevant to non-EU countries.	6

Table 1 Milestones

Deliverable No	Deliverable Name	Lead Beneficiary	Type	Dissemination Level	Due Date (month)
D1.1	Project Management Handbook	1 - UL	R — Document, report	PU - Public	3
D1.2	Data Management Plan	1 - UL	DMP — Data Management Plan	SEN - Sensitive	6
D1.3	Data Management Plan Update	1 - UL	DMP — Data Management Plan	SEN - Sensitive	18
D1.4	Data Management Plan Final	1 - UL	DMP — Data Management Plan	SEN - Sensitive	36
D1.5	Clustering Activities	1 - UL	OTHER	PU - Public	36
D2.1	Framework of NBS categorization and bestpractice	2 - NATURALIS	R — Document, report	PU - Public	6
D2.2	Framework of NBS categorization and bestpractice update	2 - NATURALIS	R — Document, report	PU - Public	24

D2.3	Initial decision-tree tool for selection of NBS in Europe	2 - NATURALIS	DEM — Demonstrator, pilot, prototype	PU - Public	24
D2.4	Decision-tree tool for selection of NBS in Europe	2 - NATURALIS	DEM — Demonstrator, pilot, prototype	PU - Public	36
D3.1	Biodiversity and ecosystem valuation classification	3 - UGOT	R — Document, report	PU - Public	12
D3.2	Policy Brief Biodiversity and ecosystem valuation classification	3 - UGOT	R — Document, report	PU - Public	18
D3.3	Report on NBS stakeholder's economic valuation	3 - UGOT	DEM — Demonstrator, pilot, prototype	PU - Public	24
D4.1	Initial Biodiversity data for financial transactions	4 - UM	DEM — Demonstrator, pilot, prototype	PU - Public	12
D4.2	Biodiversity data for financial transactions	4 - UM	DEM — Demonstrator, pilot, prototype	PU - Public	36
D4.3	Biodiversity data standard and underwriting framework	4 - UM	R — Document, report	PU - Public	24
D4.4	NBS Decision Support Tool (NBS Dashboard) v1	4 - UM	R — Document, report	PU - Public	18
D4.5	NBS Decision Support Tool (NBS Dashboard)	4 - UM	R — Document, report	PU - Public	36
D5.1	Report on 'Financial Institutions & Markets Biodiv. Data Systems Capability'	1 - UL	R — Document, report	PU - Public	14
D5.2	NBS Dashboard Proof-of-Concept Design and Implementation (lean approach with high frequency feedback loops with NBS users)	1 - UL	DEM — Demonstrator, pilot, prototype	PU - Public	30
D5.3	Adoption pathways for biodiversity linked investments v1	1 - UL	R — Document, report	PU - Public	24
D5.4	Adoption pathways for biodiversity linked investments	1 - UL	R — Document, report	PU - Public	36
D6.1	Coordination of learning sites for BIOFIN use case demonstrators v1	1 - UL	DEM — Demonstrator, pilot, prototype	PU - Public	10
D6.2	Coordination of learning sites for BIOFIN use case demonstrators	1 - UL	DEM — Demonstrator, pilot, prototype	PU - Public	24
D6.3	Report of 'Nature Finance Best Practice'	13 - QUB	R — Document, report	PU - Public	30
D6.4	Policy/Brief Report on 'NBS Multifunctionality, Business Model Design and EU Policy'	13 - QUB	R — Document, report	PU - Public	34

D6.5	Report on 'Civil Society Forum on NatureFinance'	13 - QUB	R — Document, report	PU - Public	36
D7.1	Dissemination, exploitation, communication plan M3	5 - RAINNO	R — Document, report	PU - Public	3
D7.2	Dissemination, exploitation, communication plan M12	5 - RAINNO	R — Document, report	PU - Public	12
D7.3	Dissemination, exploitation, communication plan M24	5 - RAINNO	R — Document, report	PU - Public	24
D7.4	Dissemination, exploitation, communication plan M36	5 - RAINNO	R — Document, report	PU - Public	36
D7.5	Integrated toolset for Multiplying Impact v1	5 - RAINNO	R — Document, report	PU - Public	12
D7.6	Integrated toolset for Multiplying Impact v2	5 - RAINNO	R — Document, report	PU - Public	24
D7.7	Integrated toolset for Multiplying Impact	5 - RAINNO	R — Document, report	PU - Public	36
D8.1	OEI - Requirement No. 1	1 - UL	ETHICS	SEN Sensitive	6
D8.2	OEI - Requirement No. 2	1 - UL	ETHICS	SEN Sensitive	18
D8.3	OEI - Requirement No. 3	1 - UL	ETHICS	SEN Sensitive	36

Table 2 Deliverables

The labels used mean:

- **Public** — fully open (automatically posted online)
- **Sensitive** — limited under the conditions of the Grant Agreement
- **EU classified** — RESTREINT-UE/EU-RESTRICTED, CONFIDENTIEL-UE/EU-CONFIDENTIAL, SECRET-UE/EU-SECRET under Decision 2015/444

1.3.3. Work Packages

BIOFIN-EU will achieve these outcomes, milestones and deliverables through seven work packages (WP1-WP7) within a 36-month period. WPs are designed to be mutually supportive: connected and contributing to one another. WP2 will collect, evaluate and identify the existing best-practices and will derive the requirements to be used as guidelines for BIOFIN implementation. WP3 will establish the economic valuation associated with ecosystem services and identify basic principles around how those valuations can be considered in the context of a financial instrument and/or business model (WP5). WP4 will deploy appropriate methods of data engineering and data science to ensure transparency and accuracy of data from existing-NBS as well as robust projections of biodiversity and/or ecosystems services to guide NBS investment. This will require attention to semantic interoperability barriers with a view to implementing biodiversity data standards for application in an auditing and accounting system. A data analytics and underwriting engine (WP4) will support the design of novel financial instruments and innovative business models (WP5). The creation of all KERs feed into each other at all stages of the project. WP6 will analyse NBS multifunctionality and upscaling pathways and convene a multi-actor 'policy and implementation forum.' WP1 and WP7 are cross-cutting WPs, running over the entire project period.

Figure 3. PERT Chart summarising BIOFIN WP Relationships

2. Project Management Approach

The BIOFIN-EU project management description is found in the Description of the Action (DoA), Annex 1 of the Grant Agreement (GA), as part of the contract with the European Commission (EC), along with the project scope and baselines. The Consortium Agreement (CA) is based on the contract with the European Commission and is another legal instrument establishing the rights and obligations in the relationships between partners. All other parts of project management rely on the GA and CA. Quality and risk management permeate all activities of the project and function as safeguards. Quality is assured and risks are assessed for both project products and project management practices. All activities end with the communication of decisions, changes and actions to consortium members and the EC. These are the activities that bound project management for BIOFIN-EU. Figure 4 depicts the strategy of how BIOFIN-EU project activities will be directed and managed. The core activities to ensure the project stays on track are the scope, cost and schedule management, ensuring that processes are maintained, risks are registered and dealt with effectively and efficiently. Monitoring, tracking and reporting activities will keep the project in line with what Annex 1 of the GA describes that the project should do, cost and how long it should take to accomplish its objectives respectively. The core activities of project management lead to decisions and changes in both the work of the project and its management but cannot impose practices or plans to the partners without their approval. Core activities are managed through change management, which feeds into communications management ensuring that information reaches all appropriate audiences. Quality management contributes to establishing quality control and quality assurance activities for ensuring an efficient collaboration among the consortium partners and delivery of project results, whereas the risk management is necessary for providing the process and techniques for the evaluation and control of potential project risks, focusing on their precautionary diagnosis and handling.

Directing and Managing Project Work

Figure 4 Directing and Managing Project Work

2.1. Project Management Structure

Overall, the project management strategy encompasses all the necessary mechanisms and structures for the management and administrative coordination of the project, incorporating all relevant activities, including project meetings, scope management and monitoring, cost and time management, financial audits and semi-annual technical and financial internal reporting. In the context of the project, KPI performance will be regularly monitored in the context of the Monthly WP Leaders meeting and will be reported in the aforementioned semi-annual technical internal reports. The Project Coordinator (PC) will coordinate the project from the global point of view considering all organizational, legal, and financial aspects of the project. The PC will act as the point of contact for partners in communications with the EC and ensure the submission of the official periodic reports and deliverables. The PC is only part of the governance and management structure of BIOFIN-EU, which will be appropriate for its size and complexity. In addition to the PC, it comprises a) the General Assembly (GA), the ultimate decision-making body of the consortium; and b) the Executive Board (EB) as the supervisory body for the execution of the Project, which shall report to the GA. Finally, an advisory board will be formed with members representing farmers, advisors, policy makers, ADS providers as well as a representative of the other project funded under the same topic. BIOFIN-EU will actively collaborate with similar or related projects and exchange information and knowledge as part of its Open Science approach.

The General Assembly (GA) consists of one representative of each consortium member, and it is the main decision-making body of the project. The Project Coordinator (PC) is responsible for the overall management and coordination of the project, and it is the entity acting as the intermediary between the Parties and the Granting Authority. The Project Manager (PM) is responsible for the day-to-day running of the project in terms of administrative and scientific aspects. An external Advisory Board (AB) will be formed, aiming to provide the consortium with comments and advice about financial and organisational barriers to unlocking financial flows for NBS.

The partners bring together the necessary disciplinary and interdisciplinary knowledge required to achieve the BIOFIN-EU KOs in a collaborative way. The roles and activities envisaged within BIOFIN-EU are assigned to different partners on the basis of their skills and competencies, institutional missions or business activities, taking advantage of complementarity of expertise. BIOFIN-EU's partners bring diverse and comprehensive networks of key stakeholders and leading European expertise in impactful dissemination, exploitation, activation and innovation. Partners include global networks across multiple industry sectors literacy, knowledge and awareness (SUL); creative social innovators leading new ways to activate nature-positive investments (ETIFOR) and international communication, dissemination and exploitation experts (RAIN); 38 companies in the food or food-related sector (ILSI). Based on the findings, products and impacts from the collation, activation and replication phases, academics will work closely with the learning sites to integrate their capacity building, impact driven tools into BIOFIN-EU's open access NBS Dashboard.

The hierarchical component of this project consists of the following members:

- **General Assembly (GA)** the ultimate decision-making body of the consortium, which consists of one representative from each partner authorised for taking decisions on behalf of their organisation. It is chaired by the Project Manager.
- **Project Coordinator (PC);** Responsible for the project overall and for communication with the EC and the Project Officer.
- **External Advisory Board (AB);** Provides the consortium with comments and advice about financial and organisational barriers to unlocking financial flows for NBS.
- **Work Package (WPL) Leaders;** partners responsible for Work Package related decision-making and for the preparation of input for the Project Coordinator and Advisory Board.

General Assembly (GA) is responsible for the communicating the vision and delivering the output of tasks and overall outcomes of this project, as well as delegating the necessary day-to-day activities to the team members.

The project management team consists of:

Project Coordinator (PC); Owns and drives the outcome of the project overall, helps to connect the work package outcomes and ongoing tasks to help drive the project to successful completion.

Work Package (WPL) Leaders; Work Package leaders and Task leaders are responsible for coordinating efforts in the Work Package and Task level. Reporting on the successful completion of tasks, progress on deliverables, and on problems, delays and conflicts and proposals for decision making start from the partners involved at the Task level and escalate up to the GA.

Project Manager: is responsible for supporting the PC on the day-to-day management of the project, as well as the structure and internal communication flow to facilitate an efficient project team who engage at a meaningful level for the benefit of the project outcomes.

Please note, the **Project Coordinator (PC)** retains the responsibility to intervene at any point of the management structure if the cohesion of the project is threatened. More specifically, in case of:

- Decisions which have broader project implications and/or involve communication with the Funding Authority and contradict the DoA,
- Delays, costs overruns or other lack of project progress against the objectives described in the DoA,
- Conflicts, which the Work Package leader is unable to resolve or whose resolution remains elusive for an extended period of time, threatening overall project progress.

3. Quality Management

Quality Management is a critical component of BIOFIN-EU's success as a project and to follow is an overview on the project baselines and deliverables. The project baselines will cover the scope, schedule, resources, cost and quality baselines. The deliverables throughout the project will result in BIOFIN-EU achieving the necessary project outputs and impact.

3.1. Project baselines

The project's baseline, encompassing its initial scope, cost, and schedule, serves as a yardstick to assess how actual performance aligns with the plan. It must be fully documented before project execution and control activities commence. Effective project performance measurement hinges on establishing an accurate baseline. Once the project kicks off, the baseline enters change control, facilitating the assessment of any proposed alterations and their impact. If changes are approved, the new baseline integrates the original plan with the sanctioned adjustments. The project's scope is detailed in section 2.1, while references to its original cost and schedule are provided within this chapter. Furthermore, a dedicated section outlines the quality baseline, outlining essential project indicators. These indicators serve as vital tools in performance management, aiding in gauging progress toward goals and meeting fundamental requirements.

3.1.1. Scope Baseline

BIOFIN-EU's baselines, benchmarks and assumptions:

In order to calculate the significant effects of BIOFIN-EU, the following baselines, assumptions and benchmarks were taken into consideration:

- The NBS Dashboard activation: The BIOFIN-EU learning sites are already established and present real-life case studies of best practice (exemplars) or innovative action (explorers) to collate, co-design and test concepts, tools and methodologies.
- Assumptions for economic valuations: The economic valuation of ecosystem services and biodiversity (WP4), which provides baseline data for biodiversity-linked securities and financing decisions. The approaches considered here measure individual and corporate preferences for the environment, and thus only include anthropocentric values of biodiversity.

Scope baseline is displayed by Table 1.1 on the Grant Agreement based on the strategic outcomes (SO), which define each strategic objective, BIOFIN-EU Contribution, and gives details on the linked deliverables and KPIs.

3.1.2. Schedule Baseline

The Overall Gantt chart in section 3.1.2 "Gantt Chart" within Part B of the Description of Action (DoA), presents the schedule baseline of the project. It can also be found to follow here:

Figure 5 Gantt Chart of Deliverables, Timeline and Work Package

3.1.3. Resource Calendar

ii. The resource calendar provides an overview of the anticipated effort per Work Package (WP) in person-months for the entire project duration. This calculation is based on aggregating the individual planned resource efforts contributed by each partner at the project’s outset.

iii. At the project’s inception, each WP leader submitted their planned efforts for the entire project duration, specifically related to the tasks where assigned person-months are allocated. The Project Coordinator (PC) is responsible for maintaining a consolidated version of this resource calendar throughout the project lifecycle, with the support of the Project Manager (PM).

3.1.4. Cost Baseline

The cost baseline pertains to the projected total cost of the project and the anticipated timing of expenditure throughout its duration. This calculation is derived from several key components:

1. Project Budget: As declared in the table of Annex 2 of the Grant Agreement under “Estimated budget for the action.”
2. Effort Allocation: As specified in the table of section “Staff Effort” within Annex 1 of the Grant Agreement.
3. Project Work Plan: Described in Annex 1 of the Grant Agreement, 3.1

Essentially, the cost baseline translates efforts into personnel costs per month, encompassing indirect expenses, other costs, and subcontracting fees. To calculate the project's cost baseline, the same approach used for defining the resource calendar (as explained earlier) is applied. At the project's outset, all consortium partners must provide the Project Coordinator (PC) with their planned expenses for each reporting period. Additionally, if their average person rate differs from what is documented in Annex 1 of the Grant Agreement, they should specify it. Every six months and at the end of each reporting period (M18 & M36), partners will be requested to provide an overview of the actual incurred costs.

3.1.5. Quality Baseline

EU Project, aiding in measuring progress toward achieving their objectives. It is essential that these KPIs are both quantifiable and pivotal to the project's success. In Part B of the Declaration of Acceptance (DoA), specific performance indicators are outlined to meet the project's objectives. Throughout the project's duration, the completion of these KPIs will be closely monitored via scope and change management processes. This ensures that all partners can actively contribute to discussions and help select the most appropriate performance indicators for the project. Project progress will be assessed against its KPIs at various stages, including the two project reviews and additional internal quality reviews. The results of performance measurement and evaluation, including indicator values, will form part of the progress reporting submitted to the European Commission. The baseline KPIs that have been identified for the purposes of the BIOFIN-EU project are detailed in Part B of the DoA, with a consolidated view visible in Table 3.

KPI	Target Outcome (Target Value)
1.1	No. of stakeholder workshops to categorise NBS and associated governance & systems. (4)
1.2	No. of NFCs consulted to understand R&D investment-strategic planning priorities. (15)
1.3	No. of collaborations with established EU-Funded Projects (e.g. EU LIFE). (>5)
1.4	No. of reports to existing Horizon Europe partnerships (e.g. Biodiversa+; "Water4All" ,...). (6)
2.1	Proof-of-Concepts to showcase data capture and data sharing from NBS projects. (>5)
2.2	Gap analysis in NBS economic attribution e.g. water quality & health service usage. (>10 gaps)
2.3	Economics experiment/Analyses to quantify economic value of ES. (>5)
2.4	Report on Gov. Structures and Stakeholder Participation in NBS. (3 annual reports)
2.5	Contributions to major science-policy bodies (e.g. IPBES, Capacity Building Forum). (>3)
3.1	No. of learning site proof-of-concept: financial instrument linked to certification. (>5)
3.2	No. of workshops to better understand business models & certification opportunities. (>4)
3.3	No. of potential NBS investors co-designing BIOFIN proof-of-concept activity. (>15)
3.4	No. of NFCs co-designing The NBS Dashboard functionality w.r.t. Technical Screening. (>30)
4.1	No. of tools adapted for multi-criteria decision analysis (e.g. credit rating models). (>5)
4.2	No. of firms (NBA-promoters) co-designing and testing financial tools. (>15)
4.3	No. of learning sites stakeholders involved in co-design of the NBS Dashboard. (9)
4.4	No. of real-life test cases to evaluate risk scoring for biodiversity-linked instruments. (6)
5.1	Workshops on how LSs can better select, prepare for and capture financial opportunities. (>4)

5.2	No. of networks to engage in funding gap identification by NBS-category. (>5)
5.3	No. of business models tested using BIOFIN learning sites and associated EU LIFE Projects. (>7)
5.4	No. of The NBS Dashboard pilots to test barriers to SFT compliance and financial reporting. (>3)
6.1	Workshops with enabling financial services (insurance availability) to identify link w/ investment. (>3)
6.2	No. of co-designed and tested financial instruments for investment and pension funds. (>5)
6.3	No. of fund managers involved in co-design. (>10)
6.4	No. of pilots of The NBS Dashboard in fund management setting. (>3)
7.1	No. of business case simulations using BIOFIN research and learning site activity. (>8)
7.2	No. of EU Business Schools that adopt BIOFIN outputs and case studies. (>50)
7.4	No. of finance professionals participating in biodiversity linked CPD modules. (>5,000)
7.5	No. of open days to build awareness of new SFT-related tools and methods. (>10)

Table 3 Key Performance Indicators

3.2. Deliverables

The BIOFIN-EU approach to quality centres around creating deliverables throughout the project that contribute to achieving the necessary project outputs and impact. This approach involves two key areas of focus. The first is that all project deliverables are clearly identified and the second is involves consistently tracking progress throughout the project and reiterating quality control process where needed.

BIOFIN-EU primarily relies on the peer-review method to assess quality. Under this approach, deliverables are evaluated for completeness and suitability. A quality inspection involves a systematic and structured assessment of a deliverable, conducted in a well-documented and organized manner. This approach can be applied during deliverable development and to signify their completion and approval.

Figure 6 Coordination of Activities Leading to Submission of Deliverables

Each deliverable will have an internal peer review, prior to submittal to the coordinator for approval and submittal to the EC portal, sample of this to follow.

Deliverable No	Deliverable Name	WP No	Lead Beneficiary	Deliverable Leading Author	Peer Reviewer	Type	Dissemination Level	Month Due
D7.1	Dissemination, exploitation, communication plan M3	WP7	5 - RAINNO	Eleni Stogiannou	UL-John Garvey	R— Document, report	PU - Public	3
D7.2	Dissemination, exploitation, communication plan M12	WP7	5 - RAINNO	Eleni Stogiannou	ILSI-Emilie Weynants	R— Document, report	PU - Public	12
D7.5	Integrated toolset for Multiplying Impact v1	WP7	5 - RAINNO	Eleni Stogiannou	UL-John Garvey	R— Document, report	PU - Public	12
D5.1	Report on 'Financial Institutions & Markets Biodiv. Data Systems Capability'	WPS	1 - UL	John Garvey	Louis Powell	R— Document, report	PU - Public	14

Figure 9 Sample from Review Tracker

The final edition of the deliverables for submission to the EC will be organized in PDF format and stored in the SharePoint folder path: BIOFIN-EU > Project Documents > Project Management > Submitted Deliverables.

3.2.2.1. Document Formats:

To ensure consistency and compatibility across the project, specific software formats and versions of production tools will be designated for use.

Data Type	File Format	Production Tool	Version
Word processing	.docx	Microsoft Word	"Word 2013" or newer, Google Docs
Tabular spread sheet information and graphs	.xlsx	Microsoft Excel	"Excel 2013" or newer, Google Docs
Presentations	.pptx	Microsoft PowerPoint	"PowerPoint 2013" or newer, Google Docs
Project Planning	.xlsx	Microsoft Excel and Smartsheet	"Excel 2013" or newer, Google Docs
Images	.jpeg or .png or .ai	Any software tools that can produce .jpeg files	
Portable Document Format	.pdf	Any software that can produce .pdf files	
Compressed files	.zip or .7z	Any software that can produce .zip or .7z files	

Table 4 File types and software versions

Electronic documents must be compatible with and retrievable on a Microsoft Windows 7 or newer system that allows for extended filenames. Partners tasked with document delivery must provide the documents in the stated format, and if they are working with a more advanced version, they should also supply the original version, ideally compressed in a .zip file. It is advised to enable 'Track Changes' in Word documents while drafting unless the author specifies otherwise. Partners are also responsible for ensuring that images are print-ready and can be integrated into larger print materials, particularly those intended for public dissemination. The use of PDFs is confined to their ability to produce print-ready files that maintain consistent layouts across different printers, without enabling any editing features available in PDF editing tools.

4. Risk Management Plan

This section describes how risk management activities will be structured and performed. This aspect of project management is focused on outlining the process to help identify, assess and either eradicate or diminish potential hazards that could threaten the project's success. Initially, the consortium has outlined the pertinent project risks and their mitigation strategies in the Description of Action (DoA). However, risk management is an ongoing activity throughout the lifespan of the project. This involves the continual monitoring of existing risks and the identification of new ones to ensure they are managed effectively. Evaluating these risks will result in the development of suitable countermeasures aimed at either averting the risks entirely or lessening their impact to a manageable degree.

4.1. Risk Strategy

The general approach to risk management in this project is consistently assessing and evaluating known or unknown risks for the whole project duration. The intention is for each work package to manage their own risks in a standardized template and the WP Leader determines when this needs to be escalated to the Project Manager.

Figure 10 Risk Strategy

The risk management methodology consists of four steps:

- Risk identification is initially where all potential risks are identified or risks as they arise throughout the project.
- Risk quantification will be determined by using a Risk Matrix to determine impact, probability and severity of the risk.
- Risk response encompasses two potential action paths; either a Risk Mitigation Plan which dictates the specific action that will be taken to mitigate the risk, by who and by when OR if appropriate, the WP leader will escalate the risk to the Project Manager (PM).
- Risk control and report will use the RAID methodology which logs the Risk, Action, Issue and Decision.

4.1.1. Identify Risk

Risk identification is the initial review where all potential risks are identified. These could be known risks that are common in similar projects, or unknown risk that are unpredictable. An initial list of the project risks is in the Description of Action (DoA). Risk identification continues throughout the project and can be identified by any member of the consortium and its partners at any stage. If the risk is identified within the Work Package, the Work Package Leader will be responsible for receiving the flagged risk from the project member.

4.1.2. Assess Risk

Risk Quantification will use the following 5X5 risk matrix to determine the risk “score” as shown in the matrix below:

Probability	5 Almost Certain					
	4 Likely					
	3 Moderate					
	2 Unlikely					
	1 Rare					
			1 Insignificant	2 Minor	3 Significant	4 Major
		Impact				

Figure 11 5X5 Risk Matrix

4.1.3. Risk Response

Any member of the Work Package can identify a potential risk and raise it to the Work Package Leader. Risk Management will be the responsibility of the WP Leader, or a proxy nominated by the WP leader, in terms of deciphering the appropriate response or either creating a Risk Mitigation Plan or escalating to the Project Manager (PM). The conditions when the risk is escalated to the Project Manager is if the risk is rated 4 or 5 in either impact or probability or if the risk involves any dependencies from any other work package. Other risks may also be escalated based on the judgment of the work package leader. The decision-making authority for major issues will remain with the General Assembly (GA).

4.1.4. Risk Control and Report

The fourth and final key activity is risk tracking which is the activity of systematically tracking and evaluating the performance of risk mitigation actions. There is a centralised [redacted] stored in the SharePoint and this will be used by Work Package Leaders to complete once a risk has been identified within their work package, and for the PM to manage any risks, activities, issues, dependencies or interdependencies which may impact the project in any way negatively. The

risk register is stored in the SharePoint, and this will be used by Work Package Leaders to complete once a risk has been identified within their work package, and for the PM to manage any risks, activities, issues, dependencies or interdependencies which may impact the project in any way negatively.

5. Change Management Plan

The change management plan describes how the change requests throughout the project will be formally authorized and incorporated. Every member of the consortium is entitled to propose or seek amendments to the BIOFIN-EU project, adhering to the protocols outlined in the Change Management Plan. All such proposals and requests for submitting, evaluating and implementing changes to the project will be processed as specified within this document.

5.1. Change Management Approach:

The Change Management strategy establishes these principles:

- Confirm that changes align with the project's objectives and are advantageous.
- Guarantee that every suggested change is thoroughly documented, examined, and consented to, enabling effective execution and dissemination to all members of the consortium.
- Appropriately ascertain the methods for enacting the change.
- Oversee the change and its consequent effects during its execution.
- This process is structured to ensure adherence to these principles for every alteration. Through this systematic method, the BOFIN project aims to avert unwarranted modifications and concentrate its efforts on constructive changes that fall within the project's designated boundaries.

5.2. Definition of Change

In the context of the BIOFIN-EU project, "changes" refer to any modifications or alterations that are made to the project's scope, execution, or deliverables. These can include adjustments to the project's budget, timeline, objectives, or specific work packages. Changes may be necessary to adapt to evolving conditions, new requirements, or unforeseen challenges that arise during the implementation of the project.

Based on the degree to which they affect quality, such modifications might necessitate updates to the Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) Deliverables, and hence potentially the Grant Agreement with the European Commission. It is essential to record and report these changes in the project's deliverables and reports.

It is imperative that every alteration is relayed to the Project Coordinator (PC) and the General Assembly (GA) team for a thorough assessment of its implications on the project's scope, budget, timeline, and quality.

The PC is tasked with the responsibility of disseminating information about any ratified changes to all partners within the consortium. Moreover, the PC must ensure that these changes are duly reflected in the relevant project documentation, overseeing the process. Subsequently, the PC is also charged with the duty of communicating updates in documentation to the consortium partners, with the support of the PM.

5.3. Change Process

The change management process involves several critical steps to ensure smooth transitions within the project. Identification of changes to be requested is by any member of the consortium who would like to see a change being made to any number of areas of the project. The person who would like to see the change will initially look to their Work Package Leader for ease of resolution. The WP Leaders are empowered to promote change where appropriate. The Work Package Leader must escalate to the Project Manager if the change will impact the deliverables, budget or timings of the project or any other factor that prevents delivery on the objectives as set out in the Grant Agreement. The Work Package Leader can submit their request in a MS Teams form: Change Request Form (office.com) or email

biofin@ul.ie. The GA will be notified of this change and will be responsible for reviewing it. To secure approval for a change request that has caused a dispute within the GA, it is required that two-thirds of the General Assembly's votes are affirmative, provided that at least two-thirds of the assembly members are present or accounted for. Should the proposed changes affect the General Assembly itself, the assembly will seek guidance from the European Commission and proceed to initiate an amendment to the General Assembly. In instances where a change request lacks sufficient detail, it will be postponed and returned to the initiator for additional information or clarification. Moreover, if a change is considered urgent, a special session of the General Assembly may be convened to address the change before the next regular meeting of the assembly.

5.4. Change Control Process

This is the process whereby modifications to documents, deliverables, or baselines associated with the project are identified, documented, approved or rejected. If the change is at a substantial scale, the steps that BIOFIN-EU- will follow are listed to follow:

Step 1: The change requestor will identify the need for change and will submit their request via a MS Teams channel: Change Request Form (office.com) or email biofin@ul.ie.

Step 2: The WP leader will complete the first analysis on the impact of the change and determine if it is a viable request for the work package to resolve directly, or if the General Assembly needs to be involved.

Step 4: If it is a viable request, the WP leader will share the request with the General Assembly immediately if urgent, or during the next WP Leader meeting if not urgent.

Step 5: Members of the General Assembly will perform a comprehensive evaluation of how the change affects aspects such as risk, cost, timeline, quality, and project scope. They will also consult with project partners and the individual proposing the change for further details.

Step 6: At the forthcoming meeting of the General Assembly, the members will deliberate on the suggested modification. The assembly will decide on the endorsement of each change request, utilizing the information at hand, or opt to bring the matter before the Consortium for further dialogue. Should the change necessitate an alteration to the Description of Action (DoA), a consensus within the Consortium will be essential.

Step 7: Upon the General Assembly's authorization of a change, the Project Manager (PM) is tasked with revising the project's documentation accordingly. The PM will then notify all parties concerned and oversee the enactment of the change.

5.5. Change Request Evaluation Criteria

The criteria for evaluating change requests are organized based on their urgency and potential impact, as follows:

5.5.1. Priority Levels

- Emergency: This change request is urgent and necessitates swift authorization and planning.
- Standard/Low: This change request is not urgent and can be addressed at the next regular project management meeting.

5.5.2. Impact Assessment

- Critical: This change poses a significant risk that could affect the project's delivery or might lead to a contract modification.
- Significant: This requires a decision by the Project Coordinator (PC) due to its extensive impact on the project.
- Standard/Low: This is for informational purposes and can be managed at the Work Package (WP) level as it involves routine matters.

5.6. Conflict Resolution

Project and Change management activities play a crucial role in ensuring the successful execution of the project plan and achieving its objectives. Decisions are typically made by the responsible team members based on the specific tasks outlined in the Grant Agreement.

Throughout the project lifecycle, the consortium may have changes that effect multiple work packages and must come to agreements and resolutions. Initially, these agreements can be reached through informal communication, followed by official verification via email, letters, or meeting minutes. Technical issues or conflicts that fall within the existing contractual commitments (without requiring adjustments to the Grant Agreement, budget, or overall project focus) are addressed within the relevant Work Package.

In cases where conflicts arise among partners, participants can collaborate with the General Assembly (GA) to resolve them at the daily management level. If amicable resolution is not possible, the relevant provisions of the Consortium Agreement will guide the final resolution process.

6. Cost Management

This section describes how the project costs will be planned, structured and controlled. The cost management processes, and their associated tools and techniques are documented here.

6.1. Cost Management Approach

The estimated budget for the BIOFIN-EU project is set out in Annex 2. It contains the estimated eligible costs and contributions for the action, broken down by participant and budget category.

Cost Management will be monitored based on the allocation of the funding by EC, in the following categories:

A. Personnel costs		B. Subcontracting costs	C. Purchase costs			D. Other cost categories	E. Indirect costs ³
A.1 Employees (or equivalent)	A.4 SME owners and natural person beneficiaries	B. Subcontracting	C.1 Travel and subsistence	C.2 Equipment	C.3 Other goods, works and services	D.2 Internally invoiced goods and services	E. Indirect costs
A.2 Natural persons under direct contract							
A.3 Seconded persons							

Figure 12 Categories of Budget Management

6.2. Financial Recording

Every partner is required to maintain a record of the final payment and any related documents to validate the successful execution of the project and the costs declared for eligibility. These records must be preserved by the financial team of each partner post-payment and must be accessible for EC checks, reviews, audits, or investigations upon request. Each partner will provide insight into the spend to the PC on request. There are two reporting periods at a consortium level during the duration of the project, where the Project Manager will request visibility into budget against actuals from each Work Package Leaders. If the deviation is greater than 10% of the budgeted amount, the Work Package leader will present a justification as to why such a deviation exists.

The records should contain sufficient documentation to validate:

- The actual costs declared, with documents like contracts, subcontracts, invoices, and accounting records.
- The number of units declared for unit costs.
- The eligibility of the costs to which the flat rate is applied for flat rate costs (lump sums, etc.). In this case, beneficiaries are not required to identify the covered costs.
- The costs declared for the EU project should correspond with the amounts recorded in the accounts and supporting documents. These documents should be provided in their original form, not digitally, unless digital or digitized documents are permitted by national law.

If ineligible costs, significant errors, irregularities, fraud, or serious breach of obligations are identified during an audit, the consequences could range from suspension, termination, cost rejection, grant reduction to exclusion and/or financial penalties.

7. Communication Management

The communication management plan sets out the communication architecture that will be in place for the BIOFIN-EU project. The plan is primarily focused on internal communication for the purpose of managing the communications amongst the project team. There will be a brief mention of external communication also, as well as focusing on the project team directory, how to manage and monitor communications. There is a dedicated SharePoint location to provide relevant contact information for all the partners directly involved in the project.

7.1. Communication Management Approach

The GA will take central and proactive roles in ensuring effective communication within this project. Each WP leader is responsible for cascading the relevant information to their own team members and ensuring that each work package is up to date on the necessary communications. The Project Manager identifies various personas for the cascading of relevant project information. MS Teams is the focal point of all communications, as well as email, calls and meetings, dependant on what the objective of the communication is. The representative from the GA will decipher the best course of action to ensure that the communication is received from the relevant persona.

7.2. Project Team Directory

The PC, with the support of the PM, will act as the point of contact for partners in communications with the EC and ensure the submission of the official periodic reports and deliverables. maintains a listing with communication information for all people involved in the project available at the SharePoint document repository. Each partner should ensure the list is up to date. Deliverables, minutes and general documents are also available at the SharePoint repository and will be maintained by the PM.

7.3. Project Communication Channels

This segment outlines various communication matrices that capture all identified communication needs for the project, including meetings, reports, reviews, and more. It also details the characteristics of each communication type. An analysis and documentation of the project stakeholders' communication requirements will be conducted, focusing on the type, detail, and format of the information required. Documents originating from the Commission or related projects will be distributed as needed. Access to information pertaining to the project will be unrestricted for all Partners, a provision that is also included in the project's Consortium Agreement (CA).

7.3.1. External Communications

External communication with the public (including exploitation and scientific dissemination) will be managed by WP7 whereas the communication with the EC will be managed by the Project Coordinator (PC).

7.3.1.1. Communication with the Public

BIOFIN-EU's **website** (www.biofin-project.eu/) has already been developed at M3. The project's website is the primary communication and dissemination platform to enable target groups and BIOFIN-EU's stakeholders to access project development and results, and to grasp and assess the added value and the impact of nature positive financial decision

support. The website will be updated frequently and will utilise input from all partners. It will provide an overview of the learning sites, partners and links to their websites and it will host all the public dissemination deliverables, promote relevant content (news, videos, workshops, press releases, printed material, publications etc.) for key stakeholder groups, thus engaging them in the content and objectives of the project. It will also host digital visualisations of project processes and results, to make them accessible to a wider audience. Finally, the website is also mobile-friendly, increasing accessibility and maximising the impact of the project.

BIOFIN-EU's website has a twofold role as it will serve as the principal reference point for the project, explaining the project's aims, providing new updates, and documents for download and enabling access to social media accounts of BIOFIN-EU. Furthermore, it will act as a resource centre for research on topics related to NBS, providing important updates that have an impact.

All contact information of the BIOFIN-EU project will be available within BIOFIN-EU website, enabling the easiest communication with our stakeholders as well as interested individuals/ organisations through a contact form for messages (Figure 13).

A screenshot of the BIOFIN-EU website's contact form. The form is set against a background of a lush green forest. On the left, the text "Get in touch" is followed by "Send us your thoughts about the project." in a large, bold font. On the right, there is a dark blue form box containing input fields for "Name", "Email", "Subject", and "Message". Below these fields is a checkbox for "I consent to the Privacy policy terms." and a green "Submit" button. The website's navigation menu is visible at the top, including "Home", "About", "Learning Sites", "News & Events", "Resources", "Synergies", and "Contact". A "SUBSCRIBE" button is also present in the top right corner.

Figure 13: Contact form in the BIOFIN-EU website.

This form is directly linked to an email account which is managed by WP7 leader RAINNO. In addition, the visitor can find links with all the social media accounts of the projects. Consortium members have been appointed to answer technical or more general BIOFIN-EU related inquiries (Figure 14) arising from individuals/SMEs/Universities/Organisations etc. Depending on the nature of the request, questions will be answered in 3-5 working days.

Project Coordinator

John Garvey
University of Limerick
✉ John.Garvey@ul.ie

Communication Manager

Vasilis Kotsikoris
Rainno
✉ kotsikoris@rainno.eu

Figure 14: Contact information of the project coordinator and the communication manager

As means to communicate up to date BIOFIN-EU's progress and achievements as well as future events and initiatives, an online newsletter has been planned to be published every 4 months (started M04) to provide updates and relevant information to subscribers and consortium members.

Subscriptions can take place at events as well as in BIOFIN-EU's website (Figure 15). Upon Newsletter registration, BIOFIN-EU will pay special attention to security and respect of the privacy and confidentiality of the users' personal data. Newsletter recipients will be asked to provide their consent prior to sending any information related to the project. All relevant activities and aspects related to personal data will be fully compliant with the applicable national, European, and international legal framework, and the European Union's General Data Protection.

 A dark teal background with a white 'X' in the top right corner. At the top, the text 'Subscribe to our newsletter.' is written in white. Below this is a white input field with the placeholder text 'Your email address'. Underneath the input field is a checkbox with the text 'I have read and agree to the terms & conditions'. To the left of the checkbox is a green button with the text 'Sign up'. In the center, there is a white line graph with an upward-pointing arrow, decorated with several green leaves. At the bottom, the text 'Follow us on social media' is written in white, followed by five circular icons for LinkedIn, Facebook, X, YouTube, and Twitch.

Figure 15 Subscription form for the BIOFIN-EU newsletter

To establish two-way communication with the audience, BIOFIN-EU aims to have a strong social media presence. **Five media channels** (LinkedIn, YouTube, Facebook, Twitter, and SlideShare) were selected based on the following factors:

- The most cost-effective set of channels for sharing immediate updates from the project to all stakeholder groups.
- The most adequate, valid and powerful media channels for spreading and influencing with novel practices, a wide spectrum and several key stakeholders.
- The most popular social media platforms used by BIOFIN-EU's partners, to communicate and interact with their customers and other stakeholders.

Since the M1 of the project, BIOFIN-EU has been active on social media platforms (LinkedIn, YouTube, Facebook, Twitter, SlideShare) targeting to reach a diverse audience and connect with potential stakeholders who may prefer one platform over another.

Because BIOFIN-EU will be presented at numerous events, conferences, meetings as well as other occasions to disseminate project developments and results, a **presentation template (ppt)** (Figure 16), as well as a **word (doc) template** (Figure 17) have been designed in line with BIOFIN-EU graphic identity in order to maintain consistency, professionalism and promote its recognition. Additionally, more templates have been designed for several events purposes such as an **events minute's template and an agenda template** (Figures 18 & 19).

Figure 16: BIOFIN-EU Presentation Template

Figure 17: BIOFIN-EU Word Template

Figure 18: BIOFIN-EU Minutes Template

Figure 19: BIOFIN-EU Agenda Template

BIOFIN-EUs deliverable template (Figure 7) is also consistent with communication and dissemination material graphic identity and will be used by the consortium partners for the development of all project deliverables. The deliverable template has a cover page that displays the project’s logo in a prominent position, its acronym, deliverable information (number, full title, the work package number and title) as well as the writer’s information.

7.3.1.2. Communication with European Commission

The PM acts as the intermediary for all communications between the beneficiaries and the Commission. This task mainly involves correspondence with the PO on matters revolving around:

- The preparation, completion and submission of periodic reports and cost statements for the consortium.
- The preparation, completion, and submission of deliverables.

- Project and funding-related questions raised by the consortium that need explicit feedback from or agreement with the PO.

7.3.2. Internal communication

All internal communications are directed to BIOFIN-EU@ul.ie and to the Project Manager (PM) as the first point of contact.

The project will leverage modern ICT tools such as audio/video conferencing, instant messaging, email, mailing lists, and SharePoint for information sharing. MS Teams will be the focal point to connect all internal communications both formally and informally. Regular cadences of meetings of all the project hierarchy will take place based on appropriate attendance and topic relevancy. There will also be regular informative and acumen building across the consortium to align the whole project team on the specifics of each area of the project.

Additionally, partner-hosted project meetings will occur when conditions permit travel and gatherings. To maintain the project's uniformity and integrity, biannual plenary meetings will be convened, with a minimum of two each year. These sessions will concentrate on:

- Reviewing the project's progress and insights gained,
- Establishing steps and strategies to achieve the project's goals and facilitate review processes,
- Discussing the upcoming work's structure and organization for each partner and Work Package (WP)
- Crafting approaches to address challenges highlighted in prior assessments or events, and
- Planning for imminent dissemination and management activities.

Furthermore, the project may organize additional workshops or meetings in line with the work plan and the requirements identified by the project and technical management teams.

7.3.2.1. Meetings Structure and Guidelines

There will be two advisory board meetings that will take place over the duration of the project and a number of external attendances throughout the consortium, such as conferences, and webinars.

There will be two consortium meetings per year in person, and two online for connections on the project, with the intent of reducing costs and GHG emissions. If needed, virtual attendance to these meetings may be considered for the in person meeting, but attending in person is preferable to help to build the synergies within the consortium. There will also be presentations on Subject Matter Expert areas relevant to the project on a bimonthly basis to build the general acumen of the team relevant to the project.

Meeting cadences for Work Package Leaders as a General Assembly will be weekly, and there will be a second optional hour for "office hours" weekly for WP leaders to connect if they would like an opportunity to ideate or talk through specific topics where they would like a different work Package perspective on any relevant topic to the project. Each WP Leader determines the regularity of their own team meetings, but at a regular cadence of minimum meetings will take place for each WP.

7.3.2.2. Scheduling Meetings

To schedule meetings, we'll use online scheduling tools like Doodle, Calendly or similar platforms to find suitable dates for all partners, or alternatively voting polls to determine preferred dates and times. The chairperson, usually the PM, will initiate these meetings.

We aim to co-locate meetings when feasible to cut down on costs and travel time and use the aforesaid technology options for participation. The goal is to have fewer, larger meetings for cost efficiency.

7.3.2.3. Meeting Attendance

It's mandatory for all partners to attend meetings, either in person or via a representative. Participants should come prepared and engage cooperatively to facilitate effective meetings. Decision-making authority is expected from representatives during management meetings.

7.3.2.4. Agenda Setting

The chairperson will draft and distribute the meeting agenda ahead of time, adhering to the Consortium Agreement (CA). This agenda, stored on SharePoint, will outline topics and their discussion times, ensuring participants are well-informed beforehand. Partners may propose additional agenda items within the CA's timeframe. The consortium may unanimously agree to introduce new items during the meeting. Decision-required items must be clearly marked on the agenda. For virtual meetings, the announcement timeline may be shorter.

7.3.2.5. Documentation of Minutes

Meeting minutes will be promptly shared within ten days post-meeting by the chairperson. These minutes, stored on SharePoint, become official if no objections are raised within fifteen days of distribution. Decisions documented in the minutes are binding once accepted.

7.3.2.6. Role of the Chairperson

The Chairperson is tasked with circulating the agenda, leading the meeting, and sharing the minutes. They ensure adherence to the agenda, promote fairness, and confirm the accuracy of the minutes. The Chairperson also manages the meeting's timely start and end, adherence to rules, and maintenance of decorum.

7.3.2.7. Meeting Resources

A budget is allocated to each partner for meeting-related expenses, ensuring alignment with the overall project budget. Partners are responsible for their own travel expenses to attend these meetings.

7.3.2.8. Technical Conflict Resolution

Project and quality management activities play a crucial role in ensuring the successful execution of the project plan and achieving its objectives. Decisions are typically made by the responsible team members based on the specific tasks outlined in the Grant Agreement.

Throughout the project lifecycle, the consortium will encounter various technical challenges and must come to agreements and resolutions. Initially, these agreements can be reached through informal communication, followed by official verification via email, letters, or meeting minutes. Technical issues or conflicts that fall within the existing contractual commitments (without requiring adjustments to the Grant Agreement, budget, or overall project focus) are addressed within the relevant Work Package.

In cases where conflicts arise among partners, participants can collaborate with the General Assembly (GA) to resolve them at the daily management level. If amicable resolution is not possible, the relevant provisions of the Consortium Agreement will guide the final resolution process.

8. Procurement

During the project, partners will be required to acquire from third parties the following services:

- Auditing Services for partners exceeding the threshold funding value
- Organization for online or offline meetings for training, dissemination, project meetings, piloting, and validation
- Production of dissemination material
- Transportation and accommodation for travel
- Software or hardware equipment (e.g. laptops, parallel processing nodes, license software for modelling activities etc.).

9. Gender Balance

BIOFIN-EU recognises that financial flows and associated economic activity do not automatically benefit all alike, gender issues deserve special attention, to prevent inequalities perpetuating in the land-use, agriculture and other sectors where nature-based solutions are financed. BIOFIN-EU will take all the actions needed to propose innovations benefiting the female population actively proposing and implementing NBS. Starting from the co-design phase, there will be concerted efforts to propose innovations meeting the needs of women occupied by land-use, fisheries, agriculture as well as those communities contributing to biodiversity and ecosystem services. The innovation monitoring and evaluation will involve specific measures to ensure fulfilment of this requirement. Building of capacities will provide the means of equipping women with the knowledge and skills required to innovate for change. BIOFIN-EU will build upon the integration of gender dimension in project's execution to ensure gender balance in research and decision-making towards implementation of the activities, evaluation panels and other relevant advisory boards/groups of experts and foster women's empowerment according to "Horizon Europe" requirements (EU, 2021).

10. Legal & Ethical Approach

The comprehensive ethics approach of the consortium is encapsulated as follows:

- All partners have endorsed the Consortium Agreement (CA), which meticulously delineates the rights and duties of the involved entities, particularly in matters of liability, access rights, and conflict resolution.
- In the proposal phase, a thorough ethics self-assessment was executed, accompanied by the completion of an ethics issues table. Following this, the proposal was subjected to an ethics evaluation, which it successfully cleared.

The Consortium Agreement for the BIOFIN-EU project is given in article 7 of the Grant Agreement and the following are key points:

Under the Agreement, all signatory beneficiaries bear full responsibility towards the granting authority for its execution and adherence to all stipulated obligations. They are expected to implement the Agreement diligently, in good faith, and with the necessary resources, while maintaining eligibility under the EU program funding the grant.

10.1.1. Roles and Responsibilities

(a) Each beneficiary is required to:

- Keep their information in the Portal Participant Register current.
- Promptly notify the granting authority and other beneficiaries of any significant events or circumstances that could impact the action's implementation.
- Provide the coordinator with prefinancing guarantees, financial statements, certificates, contributions to deliverables and technical reports, and any other required documents in a timely manner.
- Submit data and information related to the participation of their affiliated entities via the Portal.

(b) The coordinator is tasked with:

- Ensuring proper implementation of the action.
- Serving as the communication link between the consortium and the granting authority, which includes submitting prefinancing guarantees, reviewing documents for quality before submission, submitting deliverables and reports, and informing the granting authority about payments to beneficiaries.
- Distributing payments from the granting authority to other beneficiaries promptly.

10.1.2. Delegation and Subcontracting

The coordinator cannot delegate or subcontract the tasks mentioned above, except public body coordinators may delegate certain tasks to authorized entities they control. Sole beneficiaries or similar entities may delegate tasks to one of their members. In both cases, the coordinator retains full responsibility for payments and compliance with the Agreement.

10.1.3. Internal Arrangements

- Beneficiaries must have internal arrangements for operation and coordination to ensure proper action implementation.
- If mandated by the granting authority, these arrangements should be detailed in a written consortium agreement, covering aspects like consortium organization, Portal access management, payment distribution, financial responsibilities, rights and obligations related to background and results, dispute resolution, and liability and confidentiality agreements.

These internal arrangements must align with the Agreement and not contain any conflicting provisions. The beneficiaries' collective goal is to fulfil the Agreement's terms while ensuring the action's successful implementation.

10.2. Ethics Self assessment

The BIOFIN-EU initiative is committed to adhering to ethical standards and relevant laws at EU, international and national law, including the EU Charter of Fundamental Rights and the European Convention for the Protection of Human Rights and Fundamental Freedoms and its Supplementary Protocols. This commitment extends to any new ethical issues that may arise during the grant period.

An Ethics Advisor must be appointed because human participation is expected within project implementation (including citizen, providers of NBS, actors of real-life cases from learning sites). Therefore, ethics consent will be requested with information on the project and possibility to opt out. Personal data will have to be processed (in coherence with GDPR as written) and exchange of data may occur with non-EU countries (UK, Brazil).

The project aims at ensuring the continuous and systematic integration of ethical principles and gender and culture equality in BIOFIN-EU. It will coordinate with all WP leaders to ensure that the gender and cultural dimensions are embedded in all research and innovation activities, as presented in section 1.2.4 of the proposal. The Chair of the Kemmy Business School (UL) Ethics Committee will act as ethics advisor to the project. The Chair will ensure that the project follows the appropriate ethics procedures and will provide two reports during the course of the project (M06, M24). The Chair will provide help to implement ethics and provide guidance on informed consent, data access and ethics relevant to non-EU-countries.

Annex I

Table 1.1 BIOFIN Strategic Objectives (SO)

<p>SO#1: Generate increased understanding, knowledge and awareness of nature-positive investing and identify the enabling market conditions for (EO2) by collating existing knowledge and 8 BIOFIN learning sites to categorise NBS and provide a tool (<i>NBS Dashboard</i>) for NBS investors to monitor outcomes (WP2,3 & 4).</p>		
<p>Context: Financial decision-making and investment can be impeded by high levels of information asymmetry. Creating the enabling market conditions for large-scale investment must prioritise a systematic approach to understanding, evaluating and monitoring NBS and other nature-positive investments. Challenge: Data relevant to potential NBS investment decisions may be available from disparate, heterogeneous sources and is often unstructured (e.g. habitat quality score cards, citizen science platforms, IoT or sensor data, macro-level government-held data).</p>		
<p>BIOFIN Contribution: BIOFIN will categorise the universe of NBS that exist by assembling all available (grey) literature and (EU and national) reports on biodiversity and environmental effect, interview key stakeholders in nature conservation and nature policy to obtain additional information; and select the best monitoring methods and tools to underpin biodiversity and environment impact of nature restoration and NBS.</p>		
<p>Relation to the Work Programme: <u>Mainstreaming biodiversity and ES considerations</u>, requires standardised tools and methods to capture, share and communicate data, governance structures and spillover effects.</p>		
Linked needs: SN#1, SN#2 (Ref: Section 2.3)		Lead Partners: NAT, UG, UM
Linked deliverables: D2.1, D2.2		Linked WPs/Tasks: WP2 (T.1, T.2, T.3, T.4)
KPI	Target Outcome (Target Value)	Target Value
1.1	No. of stakeholder workshops to categorise NBS and associated governance & systems. (4)	
1.2	No. of NFCs consulted to understand R&D investment-strategic planning priorities. (15)	
1.3	No. of collaborations with established EU-Funded Projects (e.g. EU LIFE). (>5)	
1.4	No. of reports to existing Horizon Europe partnerships (e.g. Biodiversa+; “Water4All”). (6)	

SO#2 Identify and help understand the success factors, drivers, costs, accruing from the mobilisation of mainstream finance (EO1), introduce new knowledge methodologies and tools (EO2) to increase

understanding and know-how of economic actors (EO3) by co-designing and activating the *Business Model Builder* (KER2, WP3,4&6) for financial institutions and service providers, NBS providers and funders, policy makers and researchers.

Context: There is an urgent need to design new business models that can redirect the flow of capital towards biodiversity restoration and protection. This requires a shift away from conventional models towards new approaches that involve multi-actor participation and robust governance structures. **Challenge:** Redirecting the flow of finance towards biodiversity and ES restoration presents new and complex challenges for financial institutions and markets, financial service providers (auditing and accounting functions) and NFCs. There exists a set of challenges that are specific to governance structures and stakeholder engagement that must be resolved and addressed.

BIOFIN Contribution: The *Business Model Builder* will provide stakeholders with a ‘*Menu of Good Governance*’ options and a ‘*Library of Stakeholder Engagement*’ that will provide a mechanism for establishing, expanding and maintaining participation in nature-positive investments. This *Business Model Builder* will include an access point for NBS providers and promoters. BIOFIN will undertake economic analysis that contributes to the Business Model Builder by identifying economic drivers and costs (economic, health,.) at various levels (NBS providers, NFCs, financial institutions and other stakeholders) (WP3).

Relation to the Work Programme: BIOFIN will i) make use of advanced digital technologies to help unlock financial flows towards biodiversity and ii) direct drivers of biodiversity decline will be understood and addressed. In identifying venues for the allocation of mainstream finance for new NBS.

Linked needs: SN#3, SN#4, SN#5	Lead Partners: <u>UG</u> , NAT, SERDA, IST, ETI, UNIPD
Linked deliverables: D4.1, D4.2	Linked WPs/Tasks: WP3(T3.1, T3.2, T3.3) WP4 (T4.1, T4.2)

KPI	Target Outcome (Target Value)
2.1	Proof-of-Concepts to showcase data capture and data sharing from NBS projects. (>5)
2.2	Gap analysis in NBS economic attribution e.g. water quality & health service usage. (>10 gaps)
2.3	Economics experiment/Analyses to quantify economic value of ES. (>5)
2.4	Report on Gov. Structures and Stakeholder Participation in NBS. (3 annual reports)
2.5	Contributions to major science-policy bodies (e.g. IPBES, Capacity Building Forum). (>3)

SO#3 Better understand the opportunities and gaps in implementing the SFT (EO2) and help integrate existing and new certification procedures as well as the data and accounting standards into decision-making processes by integrating such tools and metrics into the design of business models (WP5)

Context: Potential investors in nature-positive opportunities require a new range of skills and capacities to monitor biodiversity impacts. There are several existing market-based tools and metrics that are used within supply chains to support and streamline decision making. **Challenge:** These certification schemes can be adapted or extended so that they meet the requirements of mainstream finance under the SFT and Technical Screening. Auditing and accounting frameworks and standards must also evolve so that they are fit for purpose and can appropriately account for the incremental impact of investment on ecosystem services and biodiversity effects.

BIOFIN Contribution: using a multi-actor approach to co-design activity at BIOFIN learning sites. This activity will be used to extend prototyping of financial instruments (e.g. biodiversity credits, environmental impact bonds,) as well business models that will incorporate certification (e.g. FSC) and labelling (e.g. food products that can demonstrate supply chain transparency).

Relation to the Work Programme: BIOFIN LS specifically (LS1, LS4-LS6, see 1.2 below) address practices in agriculture, forestry, and aquaculture and the role certification and standards can play in unlocking mainstream finance to support the sustainable use of biodiversity and a wide range of ecosystems services.

Linked needs: SN#3, SN#4	Lead Partners: <u>QUB</u> , UNIPD, ETI, IST
Linked deliverables: D4.3, D5.3, D6.2	Linked WPs/Tasks: WP4(T4.3, T4.5), WP5(T5.2, T5.5), WP6(T6.1)

KPI	Target Outcome (Target Value)
3.1	No. of learning site proof-of-concept: financial instrument linked to certification. (>5)
3.2	No. of workshops to better understand business models & certification opportunities. (>4)
3.3	No. of potential NBS investors co-designing BIOFIN proof-of-concept activity. (>15)
3.4	No. of NFCs co-designing <i>The NBS Dashboard</i> functionality w.r.t. Technical Screening. (>30)

SO#4 Expand the set of methodologies and tools that support the implementation of the EU strategy for financing the transition to a sustainable economy (EO2) by challenging existing approaches to modelling the

risk and return tradeoff and integrating biodiversity and ES risk characteristics into the *Data Analytics and Underwriting Engine (KER3)*.

Context: Within NFCs, public enterprises and financial institutions, decision-making is made using well-established models and approaches that seek to optimise financial returns within a well-understood set of short- and medium-term risks. These risks typically relate to economic, regulatory or technological factors and do not explicitly include relatively complex risks associated with the natural environment. **Challenge:** The successful integration of biodiversity considerations into financial decision-making requires the availability of high-quality biodiversity and ES data from all data holders (public and private). The set of models used in financial decision-making range from relatively simple project appraisal and corporate finance methods (e.g. net present value, risk adjusted return on capital) to bespoke credit risk models used in banking and investment settings.

BIOFIN Contribution: BIOFIN will design, build and test a *Data Analytics and Underwriting Engine* that will reduce manual overhead and potential human error by (where possible) automating the ETL steps (extraction, transformation and loading) involved in taking data from its source, and producing reporting outputs. The task will also develop a suitable mechanism to visualise decision making and its impact on the final risk score providing a safeguard against potential machine-induced unintentional errors.

Relation to the Work Programme: BIOFIN will take a forensic approach to conventional models and approaches used in the decision-making processes. It will **integrate biodiversity and ecosystem services** into public and business decision-making; and co-designing, validating and communicating new approaches to tackle societal challenges in particular focusing on nature-based solutions (NBS).

Linked needs: SN#5

Lead Partners: UL, UM, ILSI, SUL

Linked deliverables: D3.1, D3.2, D5.2, D5.3, D6.1

Linked WPs/Tasks: WP3 (T3.1-T3.3), WP5 (T5.3)

KPI	Target Outcome (Target Value)
4.1	No. of tools adapted for multi-criteria decision analysis (e.g. credit rating models). (>5)
4.2	No. of firms (NBA-promoters) co-designing and testing financial tools. (>15)
4.3	No. of learning sites stakeholders involved in co-design of the NBS Dashboard. (9)
4.4	No. of real-life test cases to evaluate risk scoring for biodiversity-linked instruments. (6)

SO#5 Create, test and validate the enabling conditions for stakeholders to undertake privately financed nature-positive activities by collating all of the resources, tools and innovations developed in BIOFIN (O1-4) into an accessible support platform, *The NBS Dashboard* (KER1-3), with tailored access portals for each key stakeholder group: NBS providers, NFCs, financial institutions and services, policy makers and researchers (WP5, 6).

Context: Directly integrate ecological considerations and biodiversity data into all stages of financial project appraisal, lending and corporate finance. Support the design of business models that accelerate SFT adoption by quantifying the economic valuation of ecosystem services. **Challenge:** Increase financial and business innovation, mutual learning, replication and scaling of nature-positive investments across the EU and beyond, enabling stakeholders to develop innovative local NBS strategies to undertake protection and restoration activities. Integrate safeguarding mechanisms so that creation and destruction of ES is fully considered and made transparent within corporate decision-making. ‘Safeguarding mechanisms’ and appropriate ‘verification mechanisms’ will be specifically examined and proposed within the corporate finance domain (KPI 5.1-5.4).

BIOFIN Contribution: BIOFIN will contribute to the European SFT and unlocking corporate finance by streamlining the corporate finance decision-process in a unifying platform, *The NBS Dashboard* via: i) the *NBS Dashboard* which facilitates project appraisal alignment with the SFT by providing for the upload of biodiversity and ES data and economic data directly from heterogeneous sources, ii) *Nature-Positive Business Model Builder* combines the available heterogeneous data of the Dashboard and provides a structured framework to evaluate NBS contributions as part of Technical Screening and associated mitigation activity and iii) the *Data Analytics & Underwriting Engine* which sits behind a user-friendly front-end interface and enables integration of NBS data with conventional approaches to financial decision making.

Relation to the Work Programme: *The NBS Dashboard* provides better measurement and monitoring of biodiversity in a systematic framework that facilitates investment decision-making.

Linked needs: SN#6

Lead Partners: UL, QUB, RAIN

Linked deliverables: D5.1 D6.1, D6.2, D6.3, D7.1, D7.2

Linked WPs/Tasks: WP4 (T4.3, T4.4), WP6 (T6.3)

KPI	Target Outcome (Target Value)
5.1	Workshops on how LSs can better select, prepare for and capture financial opportunities. (>4)
5.2	No. of networks to engage in funding gap identification by NBS-category. (>5)
5.3	No. of business models tested using BIOFIN learning sites and associated EU LIFE Projects. (>7)

5.4	No. of The NBS Dashboard pilots to test barriers to SF1 compliance and financial reporting. (>3)
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SO#6 Identify and understand the features that are necessary for of nature-positive investments to qualify for large-scale investment and promotes a holistic approach that considers nature’s essential contributions to other objectives (e.g. water security, health, food) by developing multi-criteria decision making (MCDA) approaches for investors and incorporating aggregation mechanisms into the NBS Dashboard that support selection and portfolio optimisation that maximises investment impact across criteria and sectors.

Context: Modern portfolio theory (Markowitz, 1952) is a founding framework for decision-making and optimising the risk-return profile of a conventional portfolio of assets. However, investment motivated and regulated by a nature-positive remit is frequently more complex and must consider biodiversity restoration and protection as well as multiple impacts relating among other things, land rights, food and water security, human health and vulnerable populations. This holistic approach from an NBS perspective and from an asset management is not yet reconciled.

Challenge: Investment in the protection and restoration of biodiversity can deliver long-horizon benefits for capital owners, including the maintenance and extension of essential ecosystem services. The allocation of capital across multiple investment opportunities requires a portfolio approach so that the **intended benefits across multiple criteria** are optimally achieved as well as a clear view on whether the investment activity has any **principal adverse impacts** (SFDR).

BIOFIN Contribution: BIOFIN learning sites will provide real life situations to test and validate the requirements, systems and regulatory limitations that exist for pension and investment fund managers. Modelling how large-scale investment in a particular region can positively impact long-term performance of an investment or pension portfolio requires robust data and clear decision-protocols as well as a way to communicate these outcomes to capital owners.

Relation to the Work Programme: BIOFIN will integrate data from a diverse set of learning sites to best understand how private, mainstream finance can be optimised to mitigate both direct and indirect drivers of biodiversity decline and promote biodiversity restoration in line with the SFT. In this way, BIOFIN aims to contribute to the mainstreaming of biodiversity and ecosystem services into the EU pensions funds industry. The inclusion of protected areas and their networks within the BIOFIN learning sites will provide an opportunity to validate novel financial instruments and arrangements (e.g. environmental impact bonds, public-private partnerships) and their role in expanding these areas and restoring the status of species and habitats based on up-to-date knowledge and solutions. Integrate safeguarding mechanisms so that creation and destruction of ES is fully considered and made transparent within funds management.

Linked needs: SN#4, SN#5	Lead Partners: UL, QUB, UM
Linked deliverables: D4.2, D4.3, D5.3	Linked WPs/Tasks: WP4(T4.3, T4.4) WP5(T5.2, T5.3, T5.4), WP6 (T6.3)

KPI	Target Outcome (Target Value)
6.1	Workshops with enabling financial services (insurance availability) to identify link w/ investment. (>3)
6.2	No. of co-designed and tested financial instruments for investment and pension funds. (>5)
6.3	No. of fund managers involved in co-design. (>10)
6.4	No. of pilots of <i>The NBS Dashboard</i> in fund management setting. (>3)

SO#7 Increase awareness and know-how and resolve knowledge and skills gaps in the implementation of the SFT and Technical Screening and DNSH principle (EO3) and contribute to the implementation of the EU biodiversity strategy for 2030 by designing skills and knowledge accelerators (KER4) for European financial institutions and markets that draw on real-life business simulations and related tools and instruments available in *The NBS Dashboard* (KER1-3) and through a series of stakeholder interactions (workshops, questionnaires, interviews) consolidate best practice and identify the policy levers that are needed to incentivise investment and unblock impediments to progress.

Context: The SFT plan is a major policy objective that aims to leverage financial markets to support sustainable economic growth in Europe. There remain challenges in the awareness among economic actors of the implications for their existing business model and how they can document ESG risks are reorient capital flows towards more sustainable activities. The SFDR requires managers to assess and disclose how sustainability risks are considered in their investment processes, and how they consider investment decisions that might result in negative effects on sustainability factors, known as Principal Adverse Impacts (PAIs). This reorientation requires the deployment of new tools and models that help those actors evaluate risks in new ways (e.g. ‘Value-at-Risk’ is a relatively simple approach to guiding risk appetite but cannot adjust for ‘tipping points’ or ‘long-termism’).

Challenge: Financial institutions, financial services companies and NFCs have existing systems and processes for decision-making that are in many cases incompatible with the SFT and the requirements of Technical Screening.

Incremental change in one part of the financial system (e.g. lending criteria to corporates) may be hampered by inadequate data from another part of the system (e.g. corporate reporting and ongoing monitoring impacts).

Understanding where these mismatches or tradeoffs may be occurring is essential to guide policy and consolidate best practice.

BIOFIN Contribution: Drawing on the R&I foundations of BIOFIN partners as well as a series of workshops, questionnaires and interviews (WP6) BIOFIN will implement and test the implementation of the SFT and Technical Screening through its learning sites. The NBS Dashboard provides a unifying technology that will be co-designed and iterated upon during the course of the project (WP5) and activating it across-real life case studies will provide evidence for policy recommendations (WP6). BIOFIN has an extensive network across industry (DEL, ILSI), financial services (DEL) and professional and academic knowledge and assessment (SUL, IOB) to rapidly build know-how and enhance existing skills and knowledge for the current and next generation of finance professionals.

Relation to the Work Programme: Projects supported under this destination are expected, where appropriate, to provide timely scientific contributions to major science-policy bodies such as the Intergovernmental science-policy Platform on Biodiversity and Ecosystem Services (IPBES), the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC), and the Convention on Biological Diversity. They are also expected to cooperate with the Science Service project Bio-agera.

Linked needs: SN#6	Lead Partners: RAIN, QUB, ILSI, IOB, SUL, UL
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Linked deliverables: D6.2-D6.4 D7.1, D7.2	Linked WPs/Tasks: WP6 (T6.4) WP7 (T7.1-74)
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KPI	Target Outcome (Target Value)
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7.1	No. of business case simulations using BIOFIN research and learning site activity. (>8)
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7.2	No. of EU Business Schools that adopt BIOFIN outputs and case studies. (>50)
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7.3	No. of finance professionals participating in biodiversity linked CPD modules. (>5,000)
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7.4	No. of open days to build awareness of new SFT-related tools and methods. (>10)
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LIST OF WORK PACKAGES

Work packages						
<i>Grant Preparation (Work Packages screen) — Enter the info.</i>						
Work Package No	Work Package name	Lead Beneficiary	Effort (Person-Months)	Start Month	End Month	Deliverables
WP1	Coordination and Project Management	1 - UL	35.60	1	36	D1.1 – Project Management Handbook D1.2 – Data Management Plan D1.3 – Data Management Plan Update D1.4 – Data Management Plan Final D1.5 – Clustering Activities
WP2	Biodiversity Impacts & Supply of Ecosystem Services from NBS	2 - NATURALIS	71.00	3	36	D2.1 – Framework of NBS categorization and best practice D2.2 – Framework of NBS categorization and best practice update D2.3 – Initial decision-tree tool for selection of NBS in Europe D2.4 – Decision-tree tool for selection of NBS in Europe
WP3	Economic Valuation of Ecosystem Services	3 - UGOT	82.21	3	36	D3.1 – Biodiversity and ecosystem valuation classification D3.2 – Policy Brief Biodiversity and ecosystem valuation classification D3.3 – Report on NBS stakeholder's economic valuation

WP4	Biodiversity-Linked Decision Support: From Data to Financing	4 - UM	79.10	1	36	D4.1 – Initial Biodiversity data for financial transactions D4.2 – Biodiversity data for financial transactions D4.3 – Biodiversity data standard and underwriting framework
Work packages						
<i>Grant Preparation (Work Packages screen) — Enter the info.</i>						
						D4.4 – NBS Decision Support Tool (NBS Dashboard) v1 D4.5 – NBS Decision Support Tool (NBS Dashboard)
WP5	Financial Instrument Design & Business Model Innovation	1 - UL	159.00	2	36	D5.1 – Report on ‘Financial Institutions & Markets Biodiv. Data Systems Capability’ D5.2 – NBS Dashboard Proof-of-Concept Design and Implementation (lean approach with high frequency feedback loops with NBS users) D5.3 – Adoption pathways for biodiversity linked investments v1 D5.4 – Adoption pathways for biodiversity linked investments
WP6	Use-cases, Focus Groups & Learning Site Experiments	13 - QUB	109.20	3	36	D6.1 – Coordination of learning sites for BIOFIN use case demonstrators v1 D6.2 – Coordination of learning sites for BIOFIN use case demonstrators D6.3 – Report of ‘Nature Finance Best Practice’ D6.4 – Policy/Brief Report on ‘NBS Multifunctionality, Business Model Design and EU Policy’ D6.5 – Report on ‘Civil Society Forum on Nature Finance’

WP7	Impact Maximization	5 - RAINNO	106.70	1	36	D7.1 – Dissemination, exploitation, communication plan M3 D7.2 – Dissemination, exploitation, communication plan M12
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